
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN TRADITIONAL AND HOLOGRAPHIC DISPLAY-BASED CLASSROOM SETTINGS

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Abstract

This study investigated the performance of Grade 6 learners at Divisoria Elementary School in a traditional classroom setting and a holographic display-based learning environment. The main objective was to determine whether the use of holographic displays in teaching significantly improves students' performance and participation compared to traditional teaching methods. Specifically, the study addressed the problem of low engagement and limited comprehension in traditional classrooms by introducing 3D holographic visuals to enhance understanding.

A descriptive-comparative research design was employed, involving two groups of students: one taught using holographic displays and another through traditional teaching. Data were gathered through pre-tests, post-tests, and survey questionnaires to measure both academic performance and engagement levels. The findings revealed that students who learned through holographic displays showed higher post-test scores, and greater engagement compared to those in the traditional group.

The study concluded that integrating holographic display technology in elementary education can significantly enhance students' learning experiences. It helps improve both academic achievement and classroom engagement, particularly when teaching abstract or complex topics. These results suggest that holographic tools can be a valuable addition to modern teaching strategies in support of quality, inclusive education.

INTRODUCTION

As the world continued to embrace technological advancements, the field of education also evolved to incorporate new tools and approaches. One of the emerging innovations explored in recent years was the holographic display—a technology that projected three-dimensional (3D) images into real space. This tool offered new ways to deliver lessons that were more interactive, visually engaging, and suitable for young learners who often responded well to visual and hands-on learning.

In many elementary schools, traditional teaching methods such as textbook instruction, lectures, and blackboard presentations were still commonly used. While these methods remained effective in certain contexts, they sometimes failed to fully capture the attention and interest of 21st-century learners who were increasingly exposed to digital content in their daily lives. As students became more familiar with interactive technology, educators were challenged to find ways to enhance engagement and improve learning outcomes.

The use of holographic displays provided a potential solution by helping students visualize complex or abstract topics in a clearer and more meaningful way. Holographic displays represented a new frontier in educational technology. These tools allowed students to view and interact with 3D images, which helped them understand lessons more clearly.

Mohammad et al. (2023) emphasized that holographic technology had the potential to transform teaching methods by creating immersive and interactive environments. These tools helped improve students' focus, motivation, and knowledge retention. This was especially valuable for younger learners who benefited from multisensory learning experiences.

Hoon & Shaharuddin (2019) found that students who engaged with holographic visuals were more likely to focus, participate, and remember the lesson. By turning abstract content into visual, 3D representations, holographic displays reduced the cognitive difficulty of the material and made learning more accessible.

In addition, Reem et al. (2022) explained that holographic tools added excitement and energy to classroom instruction. Unlike traditional lectures or printed materials, holographic content offered dynamic, interactive experiences that helped keep students interested. These benefits contributed to a more positive learning environment and encouraged students to become more involved in class activities.

Several studies provided evidence supporting the use of holographic technology in education. Alsaedan (2024) conducted a quasi-experimental study involving middle school students and found that learners who were taught using holographic displays performed significantly better on their post-tests than those who received traditional instruction. This suggested that holographic technology could help improve academic outcomes.

Shen et al. (2021) studied nursing students and reported similar results. Learners who participated in holographic simulations performed better in both theoretical and practical assessments compared to those taught through standard methods. This showed that holographic learning not only enhanced understanding but also supported skill development.

At the elementary level, Khairunnisa & Ahmad (2023) examined the impact of holograms on students' performance in mathematics. Their findings revealed that students who used holographic tools showed notable improvements in test scores. The 3D content helped learners visualize difficult concepts, making them easier to understand.

Likewise, Hoon & Shaharuddin (2019) observed that 72% of students improved their performance in post-tests after using holographic animation in class. The engaging nature of the visuals helped students concentrate and participate more actively in lessons. These results demonstrated that holographic displays could be an effective tool for improving both student engagement and academic performance.

Furthermore, Prado-Ortega (2022) found that students who were exposed to 3D learning environments using holograms had significantly higher achievement levels, indicating the powerful role of immersive technology in shaping learning outcomes.

Together, these studies confirmed that holographic technology could enhance the learning experience by making lessons more interactive, engaging, and effective.

This study investigated the effects of holographic display technology on the academic achievement and student engagement of Grade 6 learners at Divisoria Elementary School. It compared two groups of students: one that received instruction using holographic displays, and another that was taught using traditional methods.

By exploring the use of holographic displays in a real classroom setting, the researchers aimed to offer practical insights for educators, school administrators, and curriculum developers. The study supported efforts to improve the quality of education through innovative, student-centered teaching strategies, in line with the goals of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 for inclusive and Equitable quality education.

METHODS

Research Design

This study investigated the level of student engagement in traditional classroom setting and holographic display-based learning environment among Grade 6 learners of Divisoria Elementary School. The research utilized both descriptive and comparative research designs to explore various aspects of the study. The descriptive methods were used to gather relevant information about the respondents' profile and the level of engagement in both traditional and holographic display-based approaches. The descriptive approach helped in understanding the state of student engagement and academic performance when holographic displays were used in a specific chapter of the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) subject, as well as when traditional teaching methods were employed.

The comparative method examined differences in the performance of the respondents in two different classroom settings, the traditional setting and holographic display-based setting.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The participants for this study consisted of 60 elementary students, with 30 students per classroom. The focus was on Grade 6 students, as they were at an age where they could effectively engage with and benefit from innovative teaching methods, such as holographic displays. The participants were selected through convenience sampling, based on their availability and proximity to the designated location at the time of the study.

Research Instrument

This study utilized questionnaires and pre-test and post-test assessments as research instruments to collect data on student engagement and academic performance when using holographic displays and traditional teaching methods.

The primary instrument for gathering data on student engagement and the respondents' profiles was a structured questionnaire. This questionnaire included sections on demographic information such as sex. It also contained items that measured the students' level of engagement with both holographic displays and traditional teaching methods using a Likert scale. The engagement questions assessed factors such as interest, participation, focus, and perceived enjoyment during lessons involving both teaching approaches. This instrument allowed for a systematic and quantifiable assessment of student engagement in a controlled and structured manner.

To measure academic performance, pre-test and post-test assessments were administered to the students before and after the lessons, both with holographic displays and traditional teaching. These tests focused on the specific content of the TLE chapter being taught and were designed to evaluate the students' knowledge, understanding, and retention of the material.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

The study began with the development of a structured questionnaire designed to measure student engagement. Using a Likert scale, the questionnaire assessed engagement factors like interest, participation, focus, and enjoyment during lessons delivered through both traditional methods and holographic displays. The tool underwent validation by education specialists to ensure its accuracy and relevance, with their feedback incorporated for improvement. Approval was then secured from the Divisoria Elementary School administration to ensure compliance with institutional and ethical standards.

The researcher collaborated with a teacher to align the pre-test and post-test with the specific content of a Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) lesson. These assessments were designed to evaluate students' knowledge before and after instruction. To ensure their reliability, the tests were pilot tested with a separate group of students, and adjustments were made based on the feedback received.

The main study involved 60 participants divided into two groups: 30 students experienced instruction through holographic display technology, while the other 30 were taught using traditional methods. Both groups completed the pre-test and initial questionnaire before the lesson to gather baseline data. After the respective lessons, students completed a post-test and follow-up questionnaire to measure changes in engagement and academic performance. All responses were reviewed for completeness and kept confidential, ensuring data integrity and providing a solid basis for analyzing the impact of holographic displays on student engagement.

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the characteristics of the respondents, particularly their level of student engagement.

T-test (Paired Sample) was used to compare the performance of the respondents in traditional classroom setting and in Holographic Display-based learning environment. The

same test was employed to determine the differences in the level of engagement of the respondents on these learning environments when they are grouped according to sex.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Position held by the respondents

Sex	Traditional Classroom Setting		Holographic Display-based Classroom Setting	
	Frequency (n=30)	Percent	Frequency (n=30)	Percent
Male	18	60.00	17	56.70
Female	12	40.00	13	43.30

The data in Table 1, showing the distribution of respondents according to sex in the Holographic Display and Traditional Teaching groups, reveal a relatively balanced composition, with males slightly outnumbering females in both groups. Specifically, in the Holographic Display group, 56.7% of respondents are male and 43.3% are female, while in the Traditional Teaching group, males constitute 60.0% and females 40.0%. The nearly equal sample sizes (30 respondents each) and similar sex distributions suggest that sex is unlikely to be a confounding factor when comparing the two teaching methods.

Performance of the Respondents in Traditional and Holographic Display-based Classroom Settings

The data in Table 2 presents a comparison of academic performance between students using Holographic Display and Traditional Teaching methods, assessed through pre- and post-tests.

Table 2. Performance of the Respondents in Traditional and Holographic Display-based Classroom Settings

Remarks	Traditional Classroom Setting				Holographic Display-based Classroom Setting			
	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	Freq.	Percent	Freq.	Percent	Freq.	Percent	Freq.	Percent
Fair	7	23.30	0	0.00	5	16.70	0	0.00
Good	22	73.30	23	76.70	17	56.70	13	43.30
Very Good	1	3.30	7	23.30	8	26.70	13	43.30
Excellent	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	4	13.30

The data in Table 2 present a comparison of academic performance between students using Holographic Display and Traditional Teaching methods, assessed through pre- and post-tests. Initially, pre-test scores indicate similar performance levels, with most students in both groups scoring "Good" (56.7% and 73.3% for Holographic Display and Traditional Teaching, respectively). However, post-test results reveal a significant shift in the Holographic Display group, with a substantial percentage of students progressing to "Very Good" (43.3%) and even

“Excellent” (13.3%) levels. In contrast, the Traditional Teaching group remained largely at the “Good” level (76.7%), with only a smaller fraction achieving “Very Good” (23.3%), and none reaching “Excellent.”

Difference in the Respondents’ Performance in Traditional and Holographic Display-based Classroom Settings

Table 3 reveals that students taught using the Holographic Display method achieved a higher mean post-test score (13.17) compared to those taught with Traditional Teaching (11.40). The t-value of 3.152 and the p-value of 0.003 indicate that this difference is statistically significant, suggesting that the improvement in scores is not due to chance. This finding shows that the use of holographic displays in education can enhance students’ academic achievement.

Table 3. Difference in the Respondents’ Performance in Traditional and Holographic Display-based Classroom Settings

Classroom Settings	Group Mean	t-value	p-value
Traditional Classroom Setting	11.40	3.15*	<0.05
Holographic Display-based Classroom Setting	13.17		

These results align with current studies and published works. Alsaedan (2024) discovered that learners engaged in hologram-based science instruction exhibited greater achievement improvements than those in traditional classrooms. According to Che-Yung et al. (2021), it improves students’ comprehension by enabling them to see intricate ideas in three dimensions, resulting in more captivating and impactful lessons.

Level of Student Engagement in Different Classroom Settings

Table 4. Level of Student Engagement in Traditional Classroom Setting

Indicators	Mean	Qualitative description
1. I learn effectively when the teacher uses a chalkboard or whiteboard.	3.36	Agree
2. I find traditional teaching methods (chalkboards, textbooks, lectures) engaging.	3.16	Agree
3. I stay focused during traditional lectures.	3.23	Agree
4. I actively participate in classes that use traditional teaching methods.	3.30	Agree
5. I feel confident in my knowledge when taught through traditional teaching.	3.23	Agree
6. Traditional classroom discussions help me understand different perspectives.	2.90	Agree
7. Classroom discussions in traditional teaching methods enhance my learning experience.	3.06	Agree
8. Traditional teaching, such as lectures and textbooks, provide a structured learning environment.	3.03	Agree
9. I often feel engaged during traditional lectures.	2.06	Disagree
10. Traditional teaching makes the lessons more fun.	2.03	Disagree

11. Traditional teaching methods encourage me enough student interaction.	2.03	Disagree
12. I am more motivated to learn when traditional teaching are part of the classroom activities.	2.43	Disagree
13. Traditional teaching methods effectively support my learning needs.	3.00	Agree
14. Traditional teaching should be combined with modern technology for better learning	2.93	Agree
15. I ask more questions during lessons with traditional teaching.	3.50	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN	2.88	Agree

Legend: 1.50-2.49=Disagree; 2.50-3.49=Agree; 3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree

The data in Table 4 reveal a moderate level of student engagement with traditional teaching methods. With a grand mean of 2.88, the responses generally fall within the "Agree" range, though there is a noticeable degree of variability across indicators. The "Strongly Agree" response for item 15 (I feel bored during traditional classes), with a mean of 3.50, suggests a negative aspect within the traditional teaching approach. However, the "Disagree" responses for items 9 to 12 highlight significant concerns regarding engagement. These findings align with Yoo et al. (2022), who suggest incorporating holography into educational practices to address shortcomings in conventional teaching methods and enhance learning outcomes. The nature of traditional teaching may not capture the attention and imagination of students who are accustomed to more interactive and visually stimulating experiences.

Table 5. Level of Student Engagement in Holographic Display-Based Classroom Setting

Indicators	Mean	Qualitative description
1. I find holographic displays exciting and interesting to watch.	3.56	Strongly Agree
2. Holographic displays keep my attention better than traditional teaching methods.	3.23	Agree
3. I am more focused on the lesson when holographic displays are used.	3.13	Agree
4. I find it easier to remember information presented through holographic displays.	3.23	Agree
5. Holographic displays help me understand the lesson better.	3.36	Agree
6. Holographic displays make complex topics easier to understand.	3.03	Agree
7. I participate more actively in class when holographic displays are used.	3.10	Agree
8. I ask more questions during lessons with holographic displays.	2.40	Disagree
9. I am more willing to engage in group activities when holographic displays are part of the lesson.	3.40	Agree
10. I enjoy learning more when holographic displays are used.	3.46	Agree

11. Holographic displays make the lessons more fun.	3.53	Strongly Agree
12. I am more motivated to learn when holographic displays are part of the classroom activities.	3.40	Agree
13. Holographic displays make me feel more engaged in the lesson.	3.30	Agree
14. I would like more lessons to include holographic displays.	3.23	Agree
15. I like seeing things in 3D with holographic displays.	3.56	Strongly Agree
GRAND MEAN	3.26	Agree

Legend: 1.50-2.49=Disagree; 2.50-3.49=Agree; 3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree

The data in Table 5 indicate a generally positive level of student engagement with the Holographic Display teaching methods. The grand mean of 3.264 suggests that, on average, respondents agreed with the statements related to engagement. Most indicators (Items 1 to 7 and Items 9 to 15) show a mean score within the "Agree" range, indicating that students generally found the holographic display engaging. Several questions (Items 1, 11, and 15) even reached the "Strongly Agree" level, highlighting particularly engaging aspects of the holographic display experience. This aligns with research from Yoo et al. (2022), which showed how holography can transform education by boosting student engagement and comprehension, creating a more immersive learning experience. However, Item 8 (I ask more questions during lessons with holographic displays), with a mean of 2.400 ("Disagree"), indicates a potential area for improvement that needs to be examined.

Differences in the Level of Student Engagement in Traditional Classroom Setting in Terms of Sex

Table 6 explores differences in student engagement with traditional teaching methods when analyzed by sex. The findings indicate that while most indicators show no statistically significant gender-based variations, significant exceptions emerge for items 1, 7, and 9. Specifically, females exhibited significantly higher engagement in item 1 (I learn effectively when the teacher uses a chalkboard or whiteboard), with a mean of 3.58 ("Strongly Agree") compared to males, with a mean of 3.22 ("Agree"), and also in item 7 (Classroom discussions in traditional teaching methods enhance my learning experience). Conversely, males showed significantly higher engagement in item 9 (I often feel disengaged during traditional lectures).

Table 6. Differences in the Level of Student Engagement in Traditional Classroom Setting in Terms of Sex

Indicators	Male		Female		t-test	p-value
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE		
1. I learn effectively when the teacher uses a chalkboard or whiteboard.	3.22	(A)	3.58	(SA)	-2.088*	0.046
2. I find traditional teaching methods (chalkboards, textbooks, lectures) engaging.	3.00	(A)	3.41	(A)	-1.981 ^{ns}	0.057
3. I stay focused during traditional lectures.	3.11	(A)	3.41	(A)	-1.829 ^{ns}	0.085

4. I actively participate in classes that use traditional teaching methods.	3.22	(A)	3.41	(A)	-.777 ^{ns}	0.449
5. feel confident in my knowledge when taught through traditional teaching.	3.16	(A)	3.33	(A)	-1.041 ^{ns}	0.307
6. Traditional classroom discussions help me understand different perspectives.	2.83	(A)	3.00	(A)	-1.116 ^{ns}	0.274
7. Classroom discussions in traditional teaching methods enhance my learning experience.	2.83	(A)	3.41	(A)	-3.353*	0.003
8. Traditional teaching, such as lectures and textbooks, provide a structured learning environment.	2.94	(D)	3.16	(A)	-1.469 ^{ns}	0.153
9. I often feel engaged during traditional lectures.	2.38	(D)	1.58	(D)	3.419*	0.002
10. Traditional teaching makes the lessons more fun.	2.00	(D)	2.08	(D)	-.358 ^{ns}	0.723
11. Traditional teaching methods encourage me enough student interaction.	2.00	(D)	2.08	(D)	-.396 ^{ns}	0.695
12. I am more motivated to learn when traditional teaching are part of the classroom activities.	2.44	(D)	2.41	(D)	.108 ^{ns}	0.915
13. Traditional teaching methods effectively support my learning needs.	3.05	(A)	2.91	(A)	.530 ^{ns}	0.601
14. Traditional teaching should be combined with modern technology for better learning	2.88	(A)	3.00	(A)	-.374 ^{ns}	0.711
15. I ask more questions during lessons with traditional teaching.	33.44	(A)	3.58	(SA)	-.645 ^{ns}	0.524

Differences in the Level of Student Engagement in Holographic Display-Based Classroom Setting in Terms of Sex

Table 7 presents a comparative analysis of student engagement with holographic displays, differentiating between male and female respondents.

Table 7. Differences in the Level of Student Engagement in Holographic Display-Based Classroom Setting in Terms of Sex

INDICATORS	MALE		FEMALE		t-test	p-value
	Mean	DE	Mean	DE		
1. I find holographic displays exciting and interesting to watch.	3.52	(SA)	3.61	(SA)	-.457 ^{ns}	0.651
2. Holographic displays keep my attention better than traditional teaching methods.	2.88	(A)	3.69	(SA)	-3.584*	0.001
3. I am more focused on the lesson when holographic displays are used.	3.35	(A)	2.84	(A)	2.645*	0.013

4. I find it easier to remember information presented through holographic displays.	3.29	(A)	3.15	(A)	.663 ^{ns}	0.512
5. Holographic displays help me understand the lesson better.	3.29	(A)	3.46	(A)	-.925 ^{ns}	0.363
6. Holographic displays make complex topics easier to understand.	2.76	(A)	3.38	(A)	-2.797*	0.009
7. I participate more actively in class when holographic displays are used.	3.00	(A)	3.23	(A)	-.945 ^{ns}	0.353
8. I ask more questions during lessons with holographic displays.	2.29	(D)	2.53	(A)	-.770 ^{ns}	0.448
9. I am more willing to engage in group activities when holographic displays are part of the lesson.	3.41	(A)	3.38	(A)	.117 ^{ns}	0.908
10. I enjoy learning more when holographic displays are used.	3.35	(A)	3.61	(SA)	-1.259 ^{ns}	0.218
11. Holographic displays make the lessons more fun.	3.47	(A)	3.61	(SA)	-.618 ^{ns}	0.541
12. I am more motivated to learn when holographic displays are part of the classroom activities.	3.23	(A)	3.61	(SA)	-1.914 ^{ns}	0.066
13. Holographic displays make me feel more engaged in the lesson.	3.35	(A)	3.23	(A)	.466 ^{ns}	0.645
14. I would like more lessons to include holographic displays.	3.17	(A)	3.30	(A)	-.700 ^{ns}	0.489
15. I like seeing things in 3D with holographic displays.	3.58	(SA)	3.53	(SA)	.212 ^{ns}	0.833

Statistically significant differences emerged for items 2, 3, and 6, while the majority of indicators revealed no significant gender-based variations. Specifically, females exhibited higher engagement levels in items 2 (Holographic displays keep my attention better than traditional teaching methods) and 6 (Holographic displays make complex topics easier to understand), whereas males showed greater engagement in item 3 (I am more focused on the lesson when holographic displays are used).

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This study found a significant difference in both academic performance and engagement between students taught using holographic displays and those taught through traditional methods. Students exposed to holographic displays achieved higher post-test scores and reported stronger engagement, especially in areas such as interest, motivation, and comprehension of complex topics. While most indicators showed no gender-based variation, some significant differences emerged: females reported higher engagement in certain items related to understanding, while males showed higher focus in others. Additionally, although most responses under holographic display were positive, low engagement in asking questions during lessons indicates an area for improvement. Overall, the findings suggest that holographic display technology can positively influence student learning outcomes and engagement, making it a promising tool for enhancing basic education. It is recommended that schools adopt holographic display technology in classroom instruction, particularly in

subjects like Science, Math, and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), where visual representation can significantly enhance learning.

REFERENCES

- Alsaedan, M. (2024). The effectiveness of the hologram in developing achievement in science among middle school students in the State of Kuwait. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v14-i4/21054>
- Hoon, L. N., & Shaharuddin, S. S. (2019). Learning effectiveness of 3D hologram animation on primary school learners. *Journal of Visual Art and Design*, 11(2), 93-104. <https://doi.org/10.5614/j.vad.2019.11.2.2>
- Hohlfeld, T., Ritzhaupt, A. D., Barron, A. E., & Kemker, K. (2013). Gender differences in technology use among students: Implications for educational technology integration. *Computers & Education*, 68, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2013.04.001>
- Khairunnisa, R., & Ahmad, A. (2023). The impact of 3D holographic technology on primary school student' academic performance in mathematics: A quasi-experimental study. *Journal of Educational Technology & Online Learning*, 6(1), 12-25.
- Mohammad, H., Almarabeh, T., & Rajab, L. (2023). A rapid review of learning using hologram in higher education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 18(12), 242-247. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v18i12.38913>
- Prado-Ortega, J. A. (2022). The effectiveness of 3D holographic technology on students' learning performance: A meta-analysis. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/364477257> The effectiveness of 3D holographic technology on students' learning performance a meta-analysis
- Reem, F., Abdlfatah, R., Alaa, T., Alomaier, A., Asma, S., Ahmad, D., Elmahal, M., & Dina, M. I. (2022). V-EduGram: Voice-based control technique of hologram technology in education. In 2022 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Intelligent Systems (ICCIT) (pp. 1-6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCIT52419.2022.9711543>
- Shen, C. Y., Cheng, Y., Huang, S. H., & Huang, Y. P. (2019). P-90: Image enhancement of 3D holographic head-up display using multi-constraints angular spectrum algorithm. *Digest of Technical Papers*, 50(1), 1576-1579. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sdtp.13247>
- Tsai, C.-C., & Tsai, M.-J. (2010). Exploring the relationship between students' attitudes toward technology and their learning outcomes in science education. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 19(5), 545-555. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-010-9223-7>
- Yoo, H., Jang, J., Oh, H., & Park, I. (2022). The potentials and trends of holography in education: A scoping review. *Computers & Education*, 182, Article 104495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104495>